

Integrating Cultural Diversity into Organizational Culture for Promoting Stability in Nigerian Universities: Lessons from the University of Port Harcourt

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Abstract

Organizations manage the diversity in their workforces through diverse strategies. This study investigates the influence of cultural diversity on the organizational culture of University of Port Harcourt in the areas of staff recruitment, promotion, appointment, and discipline. The theory of organizational culture guided the study. The population of the study was 1,050 senior university employees, while the sample size was 135 respondents. Stratified and purposeful sampling techniques were adopted to select the respondents. Questionnaire whose validity and reliability were ascertained through content and test-retest methods were used, alongside in-depth interview for data collection. Data analysis was through frequencies, simple percentages, and content analysis. It was found that processes of staff recruitment are based on equal opportunity and individual capabilities, but often influenced by ethnicity diversity; staff promotion is based on approved criteria; staff appointment is often influenced by ethnicity and gender diversity, while staff discipline is on the basis of standard procedures. The study concludes that effective integration of cultural diversity in the processes of staff recruitment, promotion, appointment and discipline engender stability in Nigerian Universities. It recommends that efforts should be made by universities to curb political interference in critical work processes, adhere to clear-cut guidelines and select candidates on merit to curb the increasing incidence of mediocrity.

Keywords: *Cultural Diversity, Internal Migration, Organizational Culture, Organizational Stability, Nigerian Universities.*

Introduction

All over the world, people from different backgrounds who possess diverse characteristics are expected to recognize these differences, live together, and interact with one another in the context of cultural diversity. Sociologists describe cultural diversity as the acceptance of the co-existence of various forms of knowledge, arts, morals, beliefs, laws, traditions, customs, languages, physical abilities and disabilities, religions, ethnicity, gender, and sexual orientations, etc. found among people. It also considers how people react to these diverse characteristics of human beings, choose to live together, and manage such diversity effectively (Lin, 2020). In essence, all the elements of diversity found in individuals are brought along to workplaces, according to Lin. The issue of how to manage the cultural diversity in various workforces, therefore, becomes imperative. One of the ways many organizations manage cultural diversity is to develop their unique culture and utilize it as a veritable tool to guide management in their cultural diversity-related issues with the aim of harnessing all resources in an effective and sustainable manner (Farashah & Blomquist, 2021).

Organizational culture is described by Heinz (2022) as a set of shared values and perceptions that influence all aspects of an organization, such as structure, strategy, leadership, and administrative processes. These shared beliefs and values showcase the different aspects of an organization; they determine the way employees behave and how a business or workplace is operated. People drive it, and it is expected that a network of interactions among people with diverse characteristics often interferes with the culture of an organization. Organizational culture influences an employee's entire work life commencing from the point of recruitment, placement, and orientation, performance, skills/development, discipline, and even dismissal (Gardner, 2021). The relationship between cultural diversity and organizational culture can significantly influence the success of a workplace (Fadamu, 2023).

Sabharwal (2014) notes that a strong organizational culture that embraces cultural diversity develops an environment where employees from diverse backgrounds feel valued, respected, and included in the affairs of the organization; creates a harmonious environment where diversity is not just tolerated but celebrated; promotes an innovative and adaptable environment, and contributes to its overall success and competitiveness in a globalized society (Morris, 2023; Usman Mohideen et al., 2024). This is opposed to a rigid version attributed to migration of employees in the workplace (Pilati, Sheikh, Sperotti & Tilly, 2015). These movers are different based on gender, skills, knowledge, talents, experiences, cultural backgrounds, socio-economic status, ethnicity, etc. (Farashah & Blomquist, 2021). Some of these workers are involved in internal migration, a movement involving people who move from one geographic location to another within the same country. This contributes to the rate of global migration, especially in third-world countries, and is not a new phenomenon in Africa (Akanji, 2012; International Organization on Migration, 2021).

In Nigeria, there are three recognized major ethnic groups, which are Ibo, Hausa, and Yoruba, in addition to several other equally large but minority ethnic groups found in different parts of the country (Edewor, Aluko & Folarin, 2014). Year in year out, skilled, unskilled, educated, and uneducated Nigerians migrate from one geographically delineated location to another within the country to seek better opportunities either in business or secular jobs in both private and public organizations (Oyeniya, 2013), including universities. Universities account for a significant level of employment in Nigeria. As of 2019, there were 170 public and private universities (Nigerian Universities Commission, 2019). Private, State, and Federal universities have a mixed congregation of employees who are differentiated based on gender, ethnicity, and individual capabilities and are driven by their unique experiences, talents, orientations, motivations, interests, among others (Igbafe, 2021).

However, effective integration of this diversity within critical university administration has become a major concern. Nigerian universities, therefore, face a pressing challenge in developing and maintaining stability within their work processes and environments. Integrating cultural diversity in the system while fostering a cohesive organizational culture requires thoughtful considerations and strategic planning to enable universities to meet their needs, the needs of their employees, students, other stakeholders, and society under stable environments. This holds

significant implications for effective education administration. Studies on managing cultural diversity in Nigerian universities are available. For instance, Gberevbie, Osibanjo, Adeniji, and Oludayo (2014) investigated the impact of using gender diversity as a basis for discrimination against women on the performance of academic staff in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria; Genty and Ifenowo (2025) examined how organizational values and norms can be effectively managed to promote diversity and inclusion within Nigerian tertiary institutions, while Onyia, Ile, and Egbo (2025) assessed the impact of workplace diversity management on the performance of State universities in Anambra and Enugu States, Nigeria. The study by Onyia et al. specifically examined the effect of experience diversity on career development and ethnicity diversity on quality of research output. However, much attention has not been given to the influence of gender diversity, ethnic diversity, and individual capabilities diversity on university culture concerning processes of staff recruitment, promotion, appointment, and discipline in the University of Port Harcourt. This study fills this gap in knowledge by providing answers to the question of how gender diversity, ethnicity diversity, and individual capabilities diversity influence the University of Port Harcourt culture in the areas of staff recruitment, promotion, appointment, and discipline. Moreover, while previous studies utilized a quantitative method of data collection through the questionnaire, this study adopts both the questionnaire and in-depth interviews to provide an insightful understanding of the phenomenon. This study aims to examine the impact of integrating cultural diversity in the processes of staff recruitment, promotion, appointment, and discipline on the stability of the University of Port Harcourt and ascertain the challenges encountered in managing its cultural diversity in the areas of focus.

Literature Review

There are different reasons for an organization's willingness to address cultural diversity issues ranging from the inherent benefits the organization stands to gain from the cultural diversity of the employees such as innovativeness and creativity, cohesiveness in job teams, employee initiative, problem-solving and improved productivity (Gupta, 2013; Chowdhury, 2021; Aliyu, Abubakar & Daniel, 2024). Another reason, according to Chowdhury, is the need to maintain equitable treatment for all and prevent conflicts/crises, thereby enhancing an organization's chances of achieving stability and growth in the system.

Farashah and Blomquist (2021) examined how organizational culture and cultural diversity influence the employment prospects of migrant workers in Sweden. The outcome of the study showed that organizational culture is a major determinant of the decisions organizations make with regard to their choice of cultural diversity strategy and human resource practices in the recruitment of migrant workers. In a bid to meet the needs of minority or migrant workers, some organizations recruit and place some categories of workers in jobs that do not fit with their qualifications due to cultural diversity considerations.

However, it is considered expedient that in managing cultural diversity, there should be a fit between the characteristics of a job and the skill requirements, as this fit affects employee performance. A job match occurs when an employee is allocated to a job and job designation that are in agreement with his/her level of qualifications and competence. On the other hand, it was revealed that workers who experienced discrimination in job placement were in the areas of job assignment and engagement. Such workers were not assigned suitable jobs, tasks, and responsibilities; they were not allowed to perform specific types of jobs and were compelled to work under an unattractive work environment and conditions of work. These findings were reported by Li et al. (2020) in a study examining the influence of workforce diversity management on job match, job satisfaction, and performance.

The implementation of administrative policies that encourage the recruitment and placement of persons who have relocated to Germany was examined by Lang (2020). He cited Spencer (2008), who reported that in Europe, municipal authorities have tremendous influence on the level of job and career chances available to workers from diverse backgrounds by adopting specific employment tools and policies which promote the recruitment of minority groups. Essentially, European cities implement policies that drive equitable opportunities in a diversified labour force. In Nigeria, Bamgbade et al. (2019) investigated how cultural diversity influences the culture of mining organizations in Minna, Nigeria. They reported that all the variables of cultural diversity tested had a negative link with organizational culture variables. However, race, age and disability had a positive relationship with the culture of creating awareness on policies on equal opportunity among workers. Furthermore, it was found that ethnicity and racial considerations have a significant adverse link with organizational culture in the employment processes of people with diverse cultural characteristics. The researchers concluded that firms in the mining industry will be affected if management does not address the negative relationship between cultural diversity and organizational culture.

In order to consider all cultural interests found among employees, organizations are faced with the responsibility of harnessing their differences and ensuring inclusivity, organizational stability, and performance (Nwagwu, 2016). However, challenges arise in managing different orientations and cultures when incompatibility occurs (Lin, 2020). It was found that communication barriers, prejudices, misconceptions, and misunderstandings culminate in conflicts and competition among workers from different cultural backgrounds. This situation engenders a lack of mutual understanding, fears, disaffection, and distaste for the various cultures. As a result, workers become disoriented, frustrated, demoralized, and dissatisfied with their work (Bamgbade et al., 2019; Lin, 2020). These tensions can impede cooperation among workers. Hence, the interactions among diverse cultural factors often interfere with and eventually undermine the efforts of organizations to perform well, achieve set goals, and remain stable. Furthermore, when biased considerations are given to different individual factors in dealing with individual workers, an organization is negatively affected because employees do not have enabling environments to perform well. Moreover, certain workers may feel marginalized or excluded from the mainstream organizational culture,

leading to a sense of powerlessness and disengagement. Failure to embrace and accommodate diverse perspectives can hamper social cohesion and hinder collective progress (Sayyd, 2022).

While cultural diversity can enrich organizational culture by bringing in a wide range of perspectives, ideas, experiences, and problem-solving skills, it can also challenge existing norms and assumptions within an organization. There is also a high tendency for some members of an organization to resist efforts to integrate cultural diversity into the work system. (Stone, Stone-Romero & Lukaszewski, 2007; Don-Solomon & Fakidouma, 2021; Santana, 2023). Resistance could stem from deep-rooted prejudices or the fear of suppression and intimidation by others, thereby hindering the establishment of a genuinely inclusive and harmonious atmosphere. In a study carried out by Igbafe (2021), it was found that marginalization based on ethnicity and other problems emanating from indigene-settler issues trigger both emotional and psychological challenges among university lecturers. He also reported that various categories of workers from diverse groups, who have leadership positions, become biased during staff recruitment, promotion, and dismissal, and tend to favour people who share the same cultural background with them.

Furthermore, political interference is identified by Nwachukwu, Achori, Gogo, and NcheyAchukwu (2019) as an unfavourable influence in the recruitment of lecturers for various academic positions because it undermines the principle of meritocracy and compromises the quality of services provided by those affected. This ultimately affects the quality of graduates produced by higher institutions of learning. The issue of gender bias is another challenge, according to Gberevbie et al. (2014), who concluded from their study on public universities in Lagos State that more men are favoured during recruitment, promotion, and appointment, and male staff occupy the highest managerial positions in Nigerian universities as a result of gender discrimination against women. The concepts of cultural diversity and organizational culture are dynamic because they evolve, and mutually influence and remodel each other in such a way that allows a continuous process of growth and adaptation.

Discussing cultural diversity strategies, Podsiadlowski et al. (2013) and Ortlieb and Sieben (2013), cited in Farashah (2021), outline six strategies for managing cultural diversity in organizations. The homogeneity strategy aligns employee values with dominant organizational norms to enhance person-organization fit and avoid decision-making conflicts. The blind strategy focuses on person-job fit, prioritizing skills over cultural background in recruitment. The fairness strategy promotes equal opportunities through mechanisms like quotas to support diverse hires and organizational development. The learning strategy values the fresh ideas and skills from culturally diverse workers, enhancing innovation and internal learning. The access strategy uses culturally aware migrant employees to enter new markets and serve diverse clients. In contrast, the good worker strategy involves hiring overqualified, marginalized migrant workers willing to accept lower job conditions, often filling roles locals avoid (Janssens & Zononi, 2005). However, Idris, Abdul, and Jaapar (2015) caution that poor integration of these strategies may harm organizational performance.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted the theory of organizational culture, developed by Dr. Elliot Jaques, who published a book on the concept entitled 'The Changing Culture of a Factory' in 1951. The concept is described as a set of shared values and perceptions that determine the different features of an organization. These include the organizational structure, policy, leadership style, and administrative processes. On the other hand, Deal and Kennedy (1982) view organizational culture as consisting of four elements, namely values, heroes, rites, and rituals, in addition to the communication network in an organization. The theory assumes that organizational culture is a social construct that develops from the interactions and everyday experiences found in organizations; Organizations are shaped by shared values, norms and beliefs among its members; Organizational culture is capable of influencing the behaviour, attitudes, action and productivity of its members; Organizational culture is dynamic and changes over time through the influence of factors like leadership style, external environment and, etc. (Jaques, 1951).

Organizational culture is developed by a group of persons in their quest to manage both the external environment and internal collaborations among employees. The efficacy of a particular organizational culture necessitates that all new employees learn and adapt to it, as the culture of an organization creates a central control system that shapes its operations and achievements. Thus, organizations develop unique cultures as a way of managing their collective but diverse cultural experiences.

The theory of organizational culture posits that an organization's effectiveness and stability are significantly determined by its shared values, beliefs, norms, and practices. Differences in ethnic background, gender, language, religion, individual capabilities, beliefs, and other aspects characterize cultural diversity in Nigerian tertiary institutions. The integration of cultural diversity into the culture of universities in critical areas such as staff recruitment, promotion, appointment to positions of higher authority, and discipline promotes shared identity and a sense of belonging. This has the effect of reducing intergroup tension and enhancing institutional stability and cooperation among employees. An inclusive university culture is more resilient and capable of adapting to cultural diversity, reducing internal conflict, and promoting peaceful coexistence. This concept provides an understanding of how diverse employee behaviours, characteristics, interactions, and decision-making processes are shaped by common values and norms in a university system to achieve organizational goals and stability.

Thus, organizations share common beliefs and values in order to harmonize their diverse attributes and control both human and organizational operations. Childress (2013) maintained that it is essential for any organizational culture adopted to be adaptable, aligned with the organizational mission, inclusive, and consistent.

Methods

This study adopted a mixed-method comprising qualitative and quantitative data collection methods. A survey was conducted through the use of a questionnaire and in-depth interviews to collect data from the staff of the University

of Port Harcourt based on their insightful thoughts, observations, opinions, and experiences (Mohajan, 2018). The study population is 1,050, comprising senior academic and non-teaching staff with at least 10 years of work experience. Respondents for the quantitative sampling were stratified based on the academic and non-teaching cadres. This was to ensure a fair representation of the two major cadres within the university system. Thereafter, the purposive sampling technique was adopted to select participants who have up to 10 years of work experience, guided by the sample frame (staff list) provided by the Registry section of the University, and consideration was given to gender spread. The researcher considered 120 respondents adequate for the quantitative sampling, while 15 interviewees for the qualitative sampling were determined through the data saturation method. Thus, the sample size was 135 respondents, representing 13% of the study population. The validity and reliability of the questionnaire were ascertained through content and test-retest methods. Out of the 120 copies of the questionnaire distributed to respondents, only 100 copies were completed and returned. The total number of respondents who were sampled was 115. The interviewees were selected among Heads of Departments, Deans of Faculties, Directors of Centres/Units, Deputy Registrars/Bursars, and senior academic staff. Others are the Director, School of Graduate Studies, Personnel Officer, Senior Professional Administrative and Technical Staff (SPATS), Personnel Officer (Academic), Admissions Officer, and SGS. The interviewees were purposively selected for sampling based on their availability and willingness to express their views physically. Analysis of the quantitative data was conducted using descriptive methods, including frequencies and percentages, while content analysis was adopted for the qualitative data. Secondary sources of data included articles, journals, books, and the University of Port Harcourt records.

Results

Table 1: Influence of Ethnicity, Gender, and Individual Capabilities on Staff Recruitment

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
External job vacancies are advertised based on equal opportunity.	16	49	27	8
Staff are usually informed about internal vacancies based on equal opportunity.	29	39	23	9
Employment is based on merit and individual capabilities.	24	50	21	5
Staff are employed on the basis of gender.	0	0	53	47
Staff are employed on the basis of ethnicity.	18	19	48	15

Table 1 shows the influence of ethnicity, gender, and individual capabilities diversity on staff recruitment with the following results: Majority of the respondents (65%) agree that external job vacancies are advertised based on equal opportunity; 68% of respondents agree that staff are informed about internal vacancies fairly; 74% believe that employment is based on merit and individual capabilities; A significant majority (53% disagree, 47% strongly disagree) reject the notion that employment is based on gender diversity, and 37% agree that ethnicity diversity plays a role in hiring, while 63% disagree. Overall, the data suggest that while merit-based hiring is recognized,

concerns remain about the influence of ethnic diversity in recruitment practices. This result corroborates the responses from the in-depth interviews that sometimes, job vacancies are filled without publicity as stated below:

Like the last year employment was not based on equal opportunity because there was no proper advert. It was between the University Management and their relations. It was based on family ties, friendship and social ties. It was kind of secret advert (**Interviewee_7**).

Table 2: Influence of Ethnicity, Gender, and Individual Capabilities on Staff Promotion

Statement	Strongly (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
Staff are promoted based on merit and approved criteria	48	49	3	0
Staff are promoted without consideration to gender diversity	45	52	3	0
Staff are promoted without consideration to ethnicity diversity	25	60	15	0

Table 2 presents data on the influence of ethnicity, gender, and individual capabilities diversity on staff promotions as follows: Majority (97%) of the respondents believe that promotions are based on merit and approved criteria, indicating strong confidence in a fair promotion system; Similarly, 97% of respondents agree that gender diversity does not influence promotion decisions, reinforcing the perception of gender neutrality. However, perceptions regarding ethnicity diversity, 85% of respondents agree that ethnicity does not play a role in promotion. These results highlight a general trust in merit-based and gender-neutral promotion processes.

An interviewee stated:

No, they do not consider gender and where a candidate comes from or any form of bias but it's based on merit. There are stipulated requirements and candidates who meet the requirements are promoted. The university does not discriminate against anybody (**Interviewee_10**).

Table 3: Influence of Ethnicity, Gender, and Individual Capabilities Diversity on Staff Appointment

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Contributions by staff are recognized.	15	56	21	8
Individual capabilities are considered during staff appointment.	21	44	32	3
Male staff get more university appointments than women.	1	30	45	24

Table 3 shows results for the influence of ethnicity, gender, and individual capabilities diversity on staff appointments as follows: Majority (71%) agree that staff contributions are recognized, while 29% feel otherwise; Most respondents (65%) believe that individual capabilities are considered in appointments, though 35% disagree, suggesting some concerns about fairness; Gender disparities in university appointments appear to be a point of debate, as 31% agree that men receive more appointments, while 69% disagree, indicating varied perceptions on

gender equality in university appointment decisions. However, a significant number of the interviewees stated that more men than women are appointed through elections to higher managerial positions:

General statistics show that more men than women occupy positions at the higher echelon. No female has occupied the position of Vice Chancellor in the University of Port Harcourt and most of the Principal Officers including the Deans are mostly men. Patriarchal influence prevents women from occupying higher positions where much decision-making power resides because the society wants men to occupy such positions. I can say that there is gender bias at this level (**Interviewee_1**).

Interview reports also indicate that about 20% appointments are influenced by ethnic diversity because some designated positions are reserved for staff from specific parts of the country, as stated by these interviewees below:

Well, the position of Registrar and Vice Chancellor are for Rivers State. But they also create about 20% chances for non-indigenes, especially for the Deputy Vice Chancellor positions. Some positions are meant for Rivers State and they also share them among themselves. They consider people from different ethnic groups. It is a culture now (**Interviewee_9**).

There is no law concerning it, but the university decides what to do in order to create a stable environment and any departure from it does not attract any sanction because it is not a policy of the Federal Government. Most times, the university adopts intervention strategies like this to manage inherent diversity (**Interviewee_6**).

Furthermore, processes of staff appointment, excluding that of Head of Department and Dean of Faculty, are also influenced by the interests of the Vice Chancellor, as stated by an interviewee below:

In university appointments, the words ‘deserving workers’ is relative and depends on who is in charge and the circumstances. For instance, an elected VC would first of all consider the interests and welfare of those who helped him before ascending the position. Some people tag it as those who are loyal (**Interviewee 3**).

Table 4: Influence of Ethnicity, Gender, and Individual Capabilities Diversity on Staff Discipline

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Disciplinary cases are handled through laid-down policies.	37	53	9	1
Disciplinary cases are handled without consideration to ethnicity, gender, or individual capabilities Diversity.	32	48	15	5

Table 4 examines the role of ethnicity, gender, and individual capabilities diversity in staff discipline with the following results: Majority (90%) agree that disciplinary cases are handled according to established policies, demonstrating confidence in structured procedures; A significant portion (80%) also believe that disciplinary actions are free from bias related to ethnicity, gender, or individual capabilities considerations. However, 20%

express concerns that such factors may influence disciplinary decisions. These findings suggest that disciplinary procedures are largely seen as fair and policy-driven.

Table 5: Impact of Integrating Cultural Diversity in Staff Recruitment, Promotion, Appointment, and Discipline Processes on University Stability

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Integrating cultural diversity in staff recruitment, promotion, appointment, and discipline processes promotes better understanding of role expectations, work relationships, and university goals.	60	25	10	5
Integrating cultural diversity in staff recruitment, promotion, appointment, and discipline processes promotes consistency in work processes, job performances, and stability in the university.	61	26	11	2

Table 5 examines the perceived impact of cultural diversity integration on the stability of the University of Port Harcourt with the following results: A strong majority (85%) agrees that cultural diversity enhances understanding of role expectations, work relationships, and university goals, fostering a more inclusive and cohesive work environment. Similarly, 87% believe that diversity integration contributes to consistency in work processes, improved job performance, and overall stability within the university. However, a small percentage (15% and 13%, respectively) express doubts about the effectiveness of cultural diversity in these areas. These findings suggest that cultural diversity in staff management processes is largely viewed as beneficial for promoting workplace harmony, efficiency, and institutional stability.

An interviewee stated thus:

I am not from Rivers State, but I feel at home in the university because I feel valued and recognized. See, I may not be a management staff, but my townsman is the DVC (Administration) and that makes me feel that my interests are represented here in the university. I appreciate this level of consideration, and it’s good for the progress of the university. There’s more understanding and I do my work peacefully **(Interviewee_6)**

Some interviewees also raised concerns over the detrimental outcomes of poor integration of cultural diversity factors in the system when staff recruitment or appointment is based on parameters other than merit, as stated by an interviewee below:

When appointments are given to people who do not have the capacity to deliver quality service, the productivity of the university is undermined. Some Directors of Centres run their units down due to incompetence and that is not good for the university. Maintaining standard and quality should guide all university operations. When staff are given unmerited appointments, the performance of the university will be adversely affected. I have drawn the attention of our professional body to the danger of giving people responsibilities based on reasons other than merit **(Interviewee_10)**.

Cultural Diversity Challenges in University Staffing Practices

The results show that factionalism, sectionalism, political interests, and interference in university administration and decisions affect existing university culture. There is also the challenge of staff recruitment and appointment based on ethnic diversity, family ties, and favouritism. These factors are detrimental to the system as stated below:

See, the politicians have destroyed the university. At my age, I should be able to say the truth. See what is happening now. We have allowed politics to creep into the system and it has destroyed the university. There's so much factionalism and sectionalism. I belong to this group, I belong to Paul and I belong to Apollos. So right now, you find out that even people that you know cannot deliver are given appointments because they are your loyalists and your boys or those you perceived that helped you (**Interviewee_3**).

Unfortunately, political tendencies and alignment have penetrated our universities and what happens in universities is now dictated by politicians whose interests in the university is selfish and this phenomenon is detrimental to the university system. This is breaking away from the university norms and creating new secessionist culture of running the university (**Interviewee_2**).

Yes, recruitment is based on qualification. However, there is an infraction on the employment processes because there are so many interests to satisfy right from the Government. This infraction begins from the Federal Government and other political quarters that send and recommend candidates for employment and these requests are given consideration. It affects the university adversely when most of them don't have the required knowledge, experiences among others (**Interviewee_13**).

Findings

The study reveals that the university's organizational culture is guided by its mission and philosophy, emphasizing equal opportunity and cultural diversity. This aligns with Childress (2013), who asserts that organizational culture must reflect institutional objectives to be effective and inclusive.

Recruitment processes are designed to promote equal opportunities through internal and external advertisements. However, certain vacancies are filled without adequate publicity, particularly when management exercises discretionary control over the process. While recruitment is officially merit-based, external influences such as political interference and personal affiliations often play a decisive role. This finding supports Nwachukwu et al. (2019), who highlighted the detrimental impact of political interference on recruitment in public institutions, thereby compromising service quality.

Regarding staff promotion, gender and ethnicity do not overtly influence decisions, as promotions follow predefined criteria. However, the study challenges Igbafe (2021), who observed that ethnicity often affects staff promotion decisions in universities, with management favouring candidates from similar cultural backgrounds.

Staff appointments, while formally based on individual competencies, reveal gender disparities. Men predominantly occupy higher managerial roles, whereas women are concentrated in lower administrative positions. Notably, no female lecturer has ever been appointed as Vice Chancellor, and key leadership roles remain male-dominated. This

reflects an entrenched patriarchal culture that restricts women's access to higher leadership positions, a pattern similarly observed in Lagos State public universities (Gberevbie et al., 2014).

Ethnicity influences approximately 20% of staff appointments to higher administrative positions, with certain principal positions unofficially reserved for specific ethnic groups. For instance, the Vice Chancellor and Registrar positions are typically held by Rivers State indigenes, while non-indigenes perform Deputy Vice Chancellor roles. Although the Federal Government policy does not mandate this informal arrangement, it functions as a balancing mechanism for workforce stability. Spencer (2008), cited by Lang (2020), documented similar practices in European institutions, where job allocations to minority groups were employed to enhance workplace stability, while Chowdhury (2021) emphasized the role of equitable treatment in preventing workplace conflicts. Beyond formal policies, staff appointments are often influenced by the Vice Chancellor's preferences, particularly in rewarding loyalists from vice chancellorship elections.

However, staff discipline remains unaffected mainly by gender or ethnic diversity, adhering to institutional policies perceived as fair and just. Challenges in managing cultural diversity include factionalism and sectionalism, where staff align with conflicting interest groups, leading to exclusion, disengagement, and work process disruptions. Bamgbade et al. (2019) and Lin (2020) note that workplace prejudices and misunderstandings contribute to such conflicts. Another significant challenge is political interference, which frequently supersedes university policies, creating norms that prioritize personal interests over institutional goals.

Furthermore, political interference, familial affiliations, and personal relationships occasionally influence recruitment and appointments, thus undermining meritocracy. This finding corroborates Nwachukwu et al. (2019), who observed that prioritizing such factors over qualifications diminishes institutional service quality. A crucial concern is that cultural diversity management may inadvertently facilitate mediocrity when unqualified candidates are appointed to key positions, jeopardizing academic excellence and institutional productivity.

Conclusion

Cultural diversity is a critical feature of Nigerian Federal Universities because they employ people from all parts of the country based on the policy of the Federal Character Commission. Nevertheless, the challenge lies in integrating this diversity in universities' organizational cultures in a way that promotes shared values, collaboration, inclusivity, and stability in work processes. The findings of the study revealed that while the university promotes equal opportunity and diversity, political and personal influences often interfere with the recruitment and appointment of staff to higher leadership positions. At the same time, gender disparities persist in higher leadership, favouring more men. Gender and ethnic diversity do not significantly impact staff promotions and discipline. Challenges such as political interference, favouritism, and workplace factionalism were found to distort university work processes.

This study concludes that integrating cultural diversity in the processes of staff recruitment, promotion, appointment, and discipline promotes stability in the system, leading to effective university education administration. Proper management of cultural diversity is, however, crucial to maintain institutional integrity and prevent mediocrity in leadership. Overall, integrating cultural diversity in staff management processes is beneficial for promoting workplace harmony, efficiency, and institutional stability.

Recommendations

- i. Universities should make intentional efforts to curb political interests and interference in critical work processes and university culture.
- ii. Adherence to clear-cut guidelines on job recruitment and staff appointment to higher leadership positions should be enforced in all cases by universities.
- iii. Universities should ensure that, in balancing the spread of opportunities across the different ethnic groups, care should be taken to select candidates based on merit to curb the increasing incidence of mediocrity.

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